

Virtual calculation of the B-value allowables of notched composite laminates

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Introduction

The design and certification of composite structures is based on the building block approach. This approach relies on the accurate determination of design allowables that drive the design of structures at larger scales.

These design allowables:

- Are statistically based material parameters that define an acceptable stress value for a material
- Account for the variability of the material properties and of the manufacturing process
- Are a function of the structural details and loading conditions
- Their experimental determination is an extremely costly and time-consuming process.

Analytical prediction of the notched strength based on three ply properties

Motivation:

Reduce the costs of preliminar design of composite laminates

Goal:

Develop fast strength prediction tools for the design of composite structures with stress concentrations

Finite Fracture Mechanics model already allows the prediction of notched strength of laminated composites but requires:

- Laminate R-curve
- Laminate Strength

Determined experimentally for each layup

Analytical prediction of the notched strength based on three ply properties

Final goal:

- Estimate the notched strength of different laminates

3 Ply Properties

- Longitudinal Young's Modulus
- Longitudinal Strength
- R-curve in the fibre direction

Analytical Models

- Trace Theory (Tsai et al. 2014)
- Unit Circle failure criteria (Tsai et al. 2016)
- Relation between the mode I fracture toughness with that of the 0° plies (Camanho et al. 2011)

and finally

- Finite fracture mechanics model (Camanho et al. 2012)

Furtado et al. 2017

UQ&M framework

Geometry and material variability

Distribution of notched strengths

Statistical analysis
Monte Carlo Simulations
CMH17

B-Basis allowable

Validation

Errors below 12% between the prediction and experimental results were obtained.

The proposed methodology allows not only to obtain good predictions of the average notched strengths but also the expected statistical distribution and corresponding estimation of the B-basis allowables.

	E1 [GPa]	X ^T [MPa]	R _{SS} [N/mm]	Radius [mm]	Width [mm]
Mean	171.42	2323.47	206.75	r	w
Std	2.38	127.45	26.64	2% x r	2% x w

Application: generation of design charts

The framework can be used to generate statistically representative design charts and compare the performance of different layups and materials in a preliminary stage of the design process.

These tools are particularly useful for design engineers and would otherwise be infeasible to attain as they require a large number of experimental tests or time-consuming finite element simulations to be performed.

Notched strength variation with the load direction

Design chart of the mean and B-basis value calculated by means of MCS for different hole diameters and hole diameter-to-width ratios

Concluding remarks

The proposed framework is validated successfully for the open-hole tension specimens.

The framework can be used to quickly generate design charts for notched specimens to assist engineers during the initial stages of the design process.

The UQ&M framework can be extended to other notched configurations, provided the stress distribution and energy release rate are known for those geometries and loading conditions.

References

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